

CROPS

Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe

D1.1

Project Management Plan

31 January 2024

Project funded by the European Union (GA 101131696). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Details	
Project Acronym/ Name	CROPS: Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
Project URL	http://crops-cs.eu
Project Type	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
EU Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131696
Project Start Date	1 January 2024
Project End Date	31 December 2026
Work Package	
Work Package	WP1 - Coordination and management
Deliverable	D1.1 – Project Management Plan
Due date of Deliverable	31/01/2024
Actual Submission date	31/01/2024
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable	Mariana Malta, Tânia Moreira, Ana Solange Leal (INOVA+)
Reviewed by	All Partners
Revision	4.0
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	20

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
1.0	29.1.2024	First draft shared for review and comments	Mariana Malta (INOVA+) Tânia Moreira (INOVA+)
2.0	30.1.2024	Contributions from Partners	Catarina Azevedo (INOVA+) Giovanni Maccani (IFC) James Sprinks (Earthwatch) Julia Lotina (EUN) Luigi Ceccaroni (Earthwatch)
3.0	31.1.2024	Consolidation of Contributions	Mariana Malta (INOVA+)
4.0	31.1.2024	Final Version	Ana Solange Leal (INOVA+)

Copyright

© Partners of the CROPS Consortium, 2024

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Glossary and Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CSF	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EO	Expected Outcome
EO	Expected Outcome
FSIGN	Financial Statement Authorised Signatory
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator
PMP	Project Management Panel
TL	Task Leader
WPL	Work Package Leader

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1 Essential Documents	8
1.1 Grant Agreement.....	8
1.2 Consortium Agreement.....	8
2 Project Management Structure	9
2.1 Management Structure.....	9
2.2 Work Plan – Roles & Responsibilities.....	11
3 Internal Communication	12
3.1 Project Shared Working Space - Microsoft Teams.....	12
3.2 E-mail Communication.....	14
3.3 Meetings.....	15
3.4 Tracking Tool.....	15
3.5 Conflict Resolution.....	16
4 Reporting	16
4.1 Internal Reporting.....	16
4.2 External Reporting.....	16
4.3 Submission of information in the EC Portal.....	17
5 Quality Procedures	17
5.1 Performance Indicators.....	17
5.2 Deliverables Revision.....	18
5.3 Milestones accomplishment.....	19
5.4 Project Templates.....	20
6 Risk Management	20
7 Conclusion	21

List of Figures

Figure 1 - CROPS Management Structure.....	10
Figure 2 - CROPS Shared Working Space at MSTeam.....	13
Figure 3 - CROPS Chat at Shared Working Space.....	14
Figure 4 - Standard subject title for email communication.....	14

List of Tables

Table 1 - General Assembly Composition	9
Table 2 - Work Package Description.....	11
Table 3 - Planned Meetings in CROPS.....	15
Table 4 - CROPS Expected Outcomes	17
Table 5 - CROPS Deliverables List	18
Table 6 - Work Package Description.....	19
Table 7 – CROPS Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures.....	20

Executive Summary

The Project Management Plan is intended to support partners in the effective and efficient administrative and financial management of the project while ensuring the quality of the project outcomes. It presents the procedures, structures and coordination defined to the project implementation and sets out key responsibilities for partners. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the compliance with project scheduling and the timely delivery of project results.

CROPS Project will be ruled by the following principles for a Successful Project Management:

- Good communication between partners will be paramount to the success of the project.
- Ensure that more than one person in each partner organization is aware of what is going on in each of the specific tasks.
- Elaborate drafts before the deadlines and follow-up of all the deliverables.
- Flexible assignments, parallel tasks, full time persons can adapt fast to changes in project workload.
- Promote the project and its interest to the right stakeholders to initiate the collaboration and have more easily access to information.

The Plan will be updated and changed according to the evolution of procedures and progress during the lifetime of the project.

1 Essential Documents

The fundamental binding rules that apply to the CROPS project are set out in the following documents, signed by all consortium partners:

- Grant Agreement (and its Annexes);
- Consortium Agreement.

1.1 Grant Agreement

A Grant Agreement (GA) was signed between the Project Coordinator (PC) and the European Commission (EC) before the project's start and by project partners through the Accession Form A. The GA is the legal document through which partners are made legally liable for carrying out the activities described in the Annex I of the GA, also called Technical Annex or Description of the Action.

The GA includes the following parts:

- **Terms and Conditions** contains specific information like the subject of the agreement, start date, project duration, grant and budget, rights and obligations of the parties, division of beneficiary's roles and responsibilities, among others. ***It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully.***
- **Annex 1** (includes Part A and B): also called Description of the Action, is the main reference document for carrying out the agreed work. It is based on information from Part B of the original proposal, and it is specific for every project. ***It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully to understand the overall work programme and their specific role in the project.***
- **Annex 2:** Estimated budget for the action, including some additional information on the estimated budget, namely some specific unit's costs calculations. ***For your information.***
- **Annex 3:** Accession Form for Beneficiaries to the Grant Agreement, signed by partners. ***For your information.***
- **Annex 4:** Model for Financial Statement for Reporting Period. ***For your information.***
- **Annex 5:** Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS). ***Not expected to be used.***
- **Annex 6:** Model for the certificate on the methodology. ***Not expected to be used.***

1.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) elaborated using the latest version of the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) model, which is a simple and comprehensive model Consortium Agreement, stripped of all unnecessary complexity in both content and language. This document establishes the rules that govern the relations between partners (for example: management structures and decision-making processes within the project, distribution of the Community financial contribution, rules on dissemination, use and access rights, settlement of internal disputes, etc.).

The CA is a legally binding document signed by all project partners. The European Commission is not a contracting partner to the CA, as the legal provisions which regulate the EC relations with the project coordinator and partners are laid down in the Grant Agreement (GA, see above). The Grant Agreement's regulations take priority over those of the Consortium Agreement.

During the project, the Consortium Agreement may “evolve” and may be changed by agreement of all partners, e.g. to take into account changes in the project structure, additional rules for exploitation or protection of generated knowledge, etc. Final decisions on the CA are taken by the Steering Committee (see section 2).

CROPS CA has entered into force on the 1st of January 2024 (the Effective start date) and will last for the whole duration of the GA (1st of January 2024 - 31st December 2026). **It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully and follow the agreed rules.**

2 Project Management Structure

2.1 Management Structure

The organisational structure (Figure 1) of the consortium comprises the following Consortium Bodies:

- (A) The General Assembly**, which is the decision-making body of the consortium. The General Assembly shall consist of one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as “Member”). Each Member (Table 1) shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 6.3.7 of the Consortium Agreement. The coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly.

Table 1: General Assembly Composition

Partner Organisation	Representative
INOVA+	Ana Solange Leal
Earthwatch	James Sprinks
IIASA	Dilek Fraisl
IFC	Giovanni Maccani
Outbe	Arianna Liconti
EUN	Miriam Molina

- (B) The coordinator (INOVA+)** which takes overall responsibility for managing the project and administrative support from all partners is available to the project coordinator to ensure smooth running and ease of communication for all partners involved in the project. The coordinator is also the consortium representative in communication with the Granting Authority and is mainly responsible for project reporting, project meetings and overall communication and liaising with all the Work Package Leaders (WPLs). The coordinator has the final responsibility for the success of the project and as such, oversees and monitors the full implementation.

- (C) The Scientific coordinator (Earthwatch)** which provides support to the coordinator, by assisting the technical monitoring of the project WPs and Tasks.

- (D) **The Project Management Panel (PMP) (INOVA+ and Earthwatch)** which acts on General Assembly decisions and coordinates the workflow and information flow between the project partners and the work packages. The PMP is composed of the **Coordinator**, the **Project Manager** (both members of INOVA+, the Project Coordinator), and the **Principal Researcher** (member of Earthwatch).
- (E) **The Work Package Leaders (INOVA+, IFC, IIASA, OutBe, Earthwatch)** have responsibility for continuously monitoring progress of individual WP work, including planned deliverables and ensuring progress with the tasks in the work package, coordinating efforts between the partners involved, and managing the timely generation of deliverables.
- (F) **The Task Leaders** have responsibility for continuously monitoring progress and delivery of the Task, coordinating efforts between the partners involved, and managing the timely generation of deliverables.

Figure 1 - CROPS Management Structure

2.2 Work Plan – Roles & Responsibilities

Table 2 - Work Package Description

WORK PACKAGE	TASK	LEAD	CONTRIBUTORS	DURATION
WP1 Coordination and management WPL: INOVA+	T1.1 Project planning, monitoring and management	INOVA+	All partners	M01-M36
	T1.2 Communication with the European Commission, advisory board, and independent ethics advisor	INOVA+	All partners	M01-M36
	T1.3 Quality assurance, risk and change management, and overall work-plan monitoring	INOVA+	All partners	M01-M36
	T1.4 Information and data management	INOVA+	All partners	M01-M36
WP2 Curation: Appraisal of current CS actions and their suitability for upscaling WPL: IFC	T2.1 Review existing citizen science projects and initiatives	IFC	All partners	M01-M12
	T2.2 Scalability potential assessment	IFC	IIASA, Earthwatch	M06-M18
	T2.3 Evaluation of stakeholder involvement, and potential involvement of quadruple-helix stakeholder groups	IFC	Earthwatch	M12-M20
	T2.4 Prioritization and validation workshops with experts	IFC	All partners	M20-M32
	T2.5 Current and potential synergies with Horizon Europe EU Missions and Objectives	IIASA	IFC, INOVA+	M12-M36
WP3 Replication: Protocols and strategies for the upscaling of CS WPL: IIASA	T3.1 Development of user-centred design protocols for upscaling	IIASA	IFC, Earthwatch	M06-M34
	T3.2 Development of communication strategies for upscaling	OutBe	All partners	M08-M24
	T3.3 Guidelines for stakeholder engagement, including SMEs and industry	INOVA+	IIASA, Earthwatch	M12-M26
	T3.4 Curation and development of training resources for CS upscaling	IIASA	IFC, OutBe	M12-M30
	T3.5 Ensuring the scientific relevance and legitimacy of CS activities for upscaling at the ERA level	IIASA	Earthwatch	M08-M34
WP4 Orchestration: Maximising uptake and sustainability when upscaling CS WPL: INOVA+	T4.1 Review of current open data repositories and their requirements	Earthwatch	INOVA+, IIASA	M01-M18
	T4.2 Modalities for data interoperability, FAIR principles, open software and repositories	IIASA	INOVA+, Earthwatch	M12-M24
	T4.3 Appraisal of current CS funding models and sustainability actions	INOVA+	Earthwatch	M08-M20
	T4.4 Protocol for mobilising diverse sources of funding and ensuring sustainability	INOVA+	Earthwatch	M16-M30
	T4.5 Ensuring broad societal involvement and ownership through an inclusive approach and responsible R&I	INOVA+	All partners	M12-M36
WP5 Propagation: Creating transnational communities with shared EU Mission goals WPL: OutBe	T5.1 Development of transnational CS communities with aligned EU mission goals	IIASA	OutBe, Earthwatch, IFC	M12-M36
	T5.2 Working group on establishing societal coalitions, to fully realise the benefits of CS to society	OutBe	All partners	M18-M36
	T5.3 Identification of potential 'CS champions' in public arenas and decision-making capacities	OutBe	Earthwatch, IFC, EUN	M06-M30
	T5.4 Establishing collaboration with existing CS networks and actions	Earthwatch	All partners	M01-M36
WP6 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication WPL: Earthwatch	T6.1 Plan for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results (PEDCR)	Earthwatch	All partners	M01-M36
	T6.2 Project website	Earthwatch	All partners	M01-M36
	T6.3 Communication materials: visual identity and social media	OutBe	All partners	M01-M36
	T6.4 Establishing partnerships to widen outreach and ensure uptake of project outputs	Earthwatch	All partners	M04-M36
	T6.5 Exploiting networks, RIA and other coalitions to shape future policy and shared goals	Earthwatch	All partners	M19-M36

3 Internal Communication

Appropriate communication measures will be taken to ensure that the flow of information and sharing among partners is consistent, regular, and efficient. Considering the geographical dispersion of partners and different time zones, several channels will be used in the communication process, namely:

- i. Electronic communication (e.g., emails, phone, MStTeams, etc.);
- ii. Monthly Online Consortium Meetings;
- iii. Regular meetings to progress on WPs and Tasks work;
- iv. Physical technical/management meetings (every 6 months);
- v. Project workshops and other events.

3.1 Project Shared Working Space - Microsoft Teams

A working online space has been set up within **MStTeams** for enabling communication and documents management and exchange within the CROPS partners. This working space is accessible only to those invited and granted access and permissions are provided by the coordinator team members.

3.1.1 Shared folders

 The Working Space is composed by several folders with specific purposes (Figure 1):

- **The “Admin Docs”** folder is intended to formal and contractual documents, such as the GA and the CA.
- **The “Meetings”** folder is to keep the agendas, presentations and minutes from all meetings (physical and online).
- **The “Deliverables Submitted”** folder is to keep the all the submitted deliverables for each WP.
- **A folder per WP** is created to organise the information concerning the specific activities and tasks of that WP.
- **Other folders** may be created during the implementation of the action, as needed.

 Naming and numbering the project documents should be made in a consistent manner to identify the project, document type and the version. In order to identify a document version, the date should be used, with the format DDMMYYYY. Name segments should be separated by _ and the acronym of the project that identifies the project should be included. For example:

- the draft version of Deliverable D1.1 produced on 22 January 2024 would be:

CROPS_D1.1_22012024_V01

- When sharing a revised version of the document, the partner that has provided suggestions and inputs, should include its acronym before sending the new version to the remaining partners:

CROPS_D1.1_22012024_V01_Earthwatch

- When the document is in its final version, then the naming should be:

CROPS_D1.1_DDMMYYYY_FV

Name	Modified	Modified By
Admin Docs	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
Deliverables Submitted	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
Meetings	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP1. Coordination and management	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP2. Curation - Appraisal of current CS actions and their suitability for upscaling	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP3. Replication- Protocols and strategies for the upscaling of CS	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP4. Orchestration - Maximising uptake and sustainability when upscaling CS	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP5. Propagation - Creating transnational communities with shared EU Mission goals	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
WP6. Dissemination, exploitation, and communication	3 days ago	Mariana Malta
Contacts_CROPS_Global.xlsx	3 days ago	Mariana Malta

Figure 2 - CROPS Shared Working Space at MSteam.

3.1.2 MStTeams Chat / Posts functionality

To support the working progress and assist an easy and informal exchange, partners have access to the MStTeams chatting functionality within the Shared Working Space.

Partners are encouraged to use this functionality in complement to the email.

Figure 3 - CROPS Chat at Shared Working Space

3.2 E-mail Communication

E-mailing will be used for regular communications to ensure a regular and effective communication flow between partners and other stakeholders during the project's lifespan.

 E-mail shall be the main communication tool between partners and, especially, for formal communication.

E-mails should be sent with knowledge of the coordinator/management partners.

To facilitate the recognition of electronic messages related with the project, a standard subject title is proposed, as follows: **acronym of the project + subject** (e.g.: **CROPS | Meeting Notes**).

Figure 4 - Standard subject title for email communication

Partners are encouraged to use a MStTeams to store files and preferably send emails only with link.

3.3 Meetings

To assist the project working progress, regular online and on-site meetings are planned, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Planned Meetings in CROPS

Type	Time	Description
Consortium Online Meetings	Monthly, every first Thursday of the month.	These meetings intend to observe and verify the work progress made in each of the WPs/Tasks; assist project status on a regular basis, as well as having the opportunity to discuss operational and administrative issues on a timely fashion.
Consortium On-site Meetings	Twice a year (expected). Venues to be decided later. If possible, linked to other project activities/ events.	Besides update on project working progresses, these meetings shall serve as a moment for interaction between partners and organisation of on-site activities to assist brainstorming and decision-making (such as workshops, interactive activities). These meetings constitute major milestones for planning, exchanging information among partners, assessing project progress and success (financial and technical) and for taking major decisions about project execution.
WP Dedicated Online Meetings	Regular and shorter than other meetings. WPL do decide on the best timing.	These meetings shall be coordinated by WP Leaders and scheduled to discuss a specific WP. They shall occur regularly to assist a continuous follow-up of the work being implemented.
<p><i>After each meeting, written minutes will be produced and circulated among partners with conclusions of discussions held and information about the next steps in the project/ WP/ Tasks.</i></p>		

3.4 Tracking Tool

A Tracking Tool will be developed using Excel, specifically tailored to support the partners in assessing project information. This tool facilitates a comprehensive overview of both accomplished milestones and pending tasks.

The Tracking Tool is organized in different tabs, as follows:

- **Detailed Gantt:** details the macro and micro-tasks within each Work Package;
- **Detailed Budget:** details the budget allocated to each task/ activity;
- **Deliverables:** registers the deliverables, indicating the lead partner, the reviewers, as well as the status of each;
- **Milestones:** lists the milestones and their deadline;
- **Risk Assessment:** provides a breakdown of the risks identified, as well as a section to assess the impact of the risk on the project implementation.

To facilitate the maintenance of the Tracking Tool, each project partner bears the responsibility of inputting and regularly updating information pertaining to their respective tasks.

The Tracking Tool will be monitored during the consortium meetings, and whenever required, adjustment measures/planning will be decided.

3.5 Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution procedures are included in the Consortium Agreement, in line with responsibilities defined within the organisational structure of the project. Conflicts will be solved at the lowest level possible, and preferably amicably. If an agreement cannot be reached at a task or WP level, then the Project Coordinator will mediate.

Negotiation and decisions taken by consensus will be the main tools to resolve conflicts. Should this approach and a majority decision not be achievable by the parties involved and the rest of the Consortium, an independent referee shall be appointed by the Project Coordinator. These conflict resolution procedures will be carried out in accordance with Article 11.8 of the CA.

4 Reporting

In order for the Commission/Agency to verify that the project is implemented properly, the beneficiaries must submit any information requested, and in particular the deliverables and reports detailed in the GA.

The project's grant form is Budget-based, meaning that partners need to follow a set of rules for expenses to be considered eligible (see chapter 3 of the Grant Agreement) and that specific details will be requested in reporting periods.

Two levels of reporting are to be implemented during the action.

4.1 Internal Reporting

Every nine-months, partners shall report to the PC the progress made in that specific period, namely regarding main achievements, financial execution, deviations from plans and anticipated actions for the following period. The timing for this internal reporting is as follows:

- M01-M9: 1st Internal Report
- M10-M18: 2nd Internal Report
- M19-M25: 3rd Internal Report
- M26-M36: 4th Internal Report

4.2 External Reporting

CROPS project has two Official Reporting Periods when a periodic report (technical + financial) must be submitted to the EC via the Funding & Tenders Portal:

- M1-M18: Interim Report (Jan.24 - Jun.25)
- M19-M36: Final Report (Jul.25 - Dec.26)

The technical report shall include an explanation of the work carried out, an overview of the progress and a summary for publication. Report on work progress is to be collected by WPL and provided to the PC, who will be responsible for integrating all inputs and produce the final report. Before submission to the EC, the report is to be validated by all partners.

The Periodic Financial report will include the Individual financial statement (Annex 4 to the GA), an explanation on the use of resources and a Periodic summary financial statement. It will be filled in by each participant in the Funding & Tenders Portal and signed by the Financial Statement Authorised Signatory (FSIGN).

4.3 Submission of information in the EC Portal

With exception for the Periodic Financial Report (see previous point), the Project Coordinator will submit all the information (technical reports, deliverables, milestones, etc.) in the EC Portal after this information has completed the consortium reviewing process.

5 Quality Procedures

5.1 Performance Indicators

For each of the Expected Outcome (EO) of the project, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been elaborated (Table 4) and shall be monitored closely to ensure the quantification of the outcomes of the project.

Table 4 - CROPS Expected Outcomes

Expected Outcomes	KPI description and Means of Verification
Identification of citizen science initiatives with high potential impact if upscaled to ERA level	At least 500 projects screened for inclusion in the suitability assessment
	At least 100 projects assessed
	At least 3 projects selected as suitable for upscaling per each of the 5 EU missions
Establishment of broad societal coalitions/networks of quadruple helix actors organised around promising citizen science initiatives	Uptake of design protocols and strategies regarding user-centred approaches, communication strategies, stakeholder engagement and training by at least 100 projects
	4 mutual learning workshops attended by at least 20 societal representatives, including 2 from each quadruple-helix stakeholder group
	5 Online CS community spaces targeted at each Horizon Europe EU mission
	Working group on societal coalitions, representing all quadruple-helix stakeholders (at least 5 representatives per group, at least 50 participants in total)
Protocols and working modalities for use of open transnational data repositories and infrastructures	Identification of at least 2 citizen science champions for each mission (with at least one youth representative)
	Uptake of catalogue of working modalities, protocols and guidance for data interoperability, FAIR principles and open data repositories by at least 100 CS projects
Proposals and commitments for mobilising diverse sources of funding to ensure sustainability of citizen science initiatives	Uptake of protocol and guidance for mobilising diverse sources of funding by at least 100 projects
	Proposals and identified potential commitments for funding for at least the 3 most suitable projects for upscaling per EU mission

The KPIs defined for the project will be followed-up by the PC and WPL to ensure the implementation of tasks is made in most suitable manner to achieve these targets and the overall objectives, thus maximising the impact of the action.

5.2 Deliverables Revision

The deliverables are the products of the project. Deliverables are also the evidence of the project's performance and enable the Commission to monitor the project's progress, implementation, and impact. Deliverables are identified in the Annex 1 to the GA per WP and must be submitted according to the timetable specified in the table hereafter.

The CROPS project is built on a participatory and iterative approach to ensure the active involvement of all project partners in the development and production of the project's deliverables. As a general principle, the responsibility for the content of each deliverable report is always with the author(s). This approach will serve as an internal quality review procedure to ensure technical value, accuracy and relevance of the reports developed.

The following process is proposed:

- Whenever relevant, draft deliverables are sent to all consortium members for feedback allowing them at least one week to reply.
- Each WP leader should ensure that the deliverable final draft is ready and send to the reviewer partner by the responsible partner **at least 2 weeks before due date** (see deliverable list – Table 4).
- Reviewer partner should send their final comments to the partner responsible for the deliverable **within one week**.
- The partner responsible for the deliverable must then send the very final version of the deliverable **at least 3 working days before the due date** to the PC and PMP.
- The final decision on the deliverables is taken by the PC, and PMO is the person responsible for uploading the deliverable on the Funding & Tenders Portal at the latest **on the due date and informs the EC**.

Table 5 - CROPS Deliverables List

No	Deliverable Name	WP	Due Date	Responsible Partner	Review Partner
1.1	Project management plan	1	M1	INOVA+	All Partners
1.2	Risk management plan	1	M2	INOVA+	All Partners
1.3	Data management plan	1	M4	INOVA+	All Partners
2.1	Review results and final version of the scalability assessment framework & criteria	2	M12	IFC	Earthwatch
2.2	Scalability ranking report based on potential	2	M18	IFC	INOVA+
2.3	Report on validation workshops	2	M32	IFC	INOVA+
2.4	Citizen science EU Mission roadmap	2	M33	IIASA	Earthwatch
3.1	User-centred design protocols for upscaling	3	M34	IIASA	OutBe
3.2	CROPS communication strategies for upscaling	3	M24	OutBe	Earthwatch

No	Deliverable Name	WP	Due Date	Responsible Partner	Review Partner
3.3	CROPS guidelines for stakeholder engagement	3	M26	INOVA+	EUN
3.4	Curated training resources for upscaled citizen science	3	M30	IIASA	OutBe
4.1	Open data repositories analysis report	4	M18	Earthwatch	INOVA+
4.2	Guidelines for citizen science data interoperability	4	M24	IIASA	INOVA+
4.3	Mapping of citizen science funding models	4	M20	INOVA+	OutBe
4.4	Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability - Preliminary Version	4	M24	INOVA+	IIASA
4.5	Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability - Final Version	4	M30	INOVA+	IIASA
4.6	Report on CROPS mutual learning workshops	4	M34	INOVA+	IIASA
5.1	CROPS transnational community online spaces	5	M14	IIASA	Earthwatch
5.2	Final report on societal working group findings	5	M35	OutBe	INOVA+
5.3	CROPS citizen science champions webpage	5	M10	OutBe	Earthwatch
5.4	Upscaling citizen science Special Interest Group findings	5	M36	Earthwatch	Earthwatch
6.1	Plan for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results	6	M3	Earthwatch	INOVA+
6.2	CROPS website	6	M1	Earthwatch	All Partners
6.3	CROPS MOOC for educators and students	6	M20	EUN	IIASA
6.4	Policy Brief - Citizen science and its upscaling to a transnational level	6	M34	Earthwatch	INOVA+

5.3 Milestones accomplishment

Table 6 lists the project milestones. Partners are responsible for following-up the milestones and share with the Project Coordinator and Consortium the means of verification of the reached milestone. The PC submits the evidence in the EC Portal.

Table 6 - Work Package Description

No	Milestone Name	WP	Partner	Due Date	Means of Verification
MS1	CROPS website launched	1,6	Earthwatch	M1	D6.2
MS2	Launch of transnational community online spaces	6,5	Earthwatch	M14	D5.1
MS3	Ranking of potential projects regarding scalability related to each EU mission	2	IFC	M18	D2.2
MS4	Launch of online training resources on CROPS website	3,6	IIASA	M30	D3.4
MS5	Mutual learning workshops	4,5	INOVA+	M32	workshop report delivered (D4.5)
MS6	Working group meetings on establishing societal coalitions	5	EUN	M32	meeting minutes available
MS7	Roadmap of existing and potential synergies of citizen science with EU mission goals	2	IFC	M33	D2.4

No	Milestone Name	WP	Partner	Due Date	Means of Verification
MS8	Completion of support materials for engagement, communication and user-centred design	3,6	IIASA	M34	materials available on website
MS9	All project guidance and resources published and ready for post-project uptake	4, 1, 3, 6, 2, 5	Earthwatch	M36	project website updated with all resources

5.4 Project Templates

Partners will use provided templates for project documents and presentations to facilitate their production, guarantee the consistency and quality of CROPS image and ensure that all documents produced in the framework of the project carry the mention of EU funding in the requested format.

6 Risk Management

An initial identification of risks and related mitigation measures can be found in Table 7 and this list will be updated on *ad hoc* basis, whenever new risks are identified. Risks will be assessed separately and will be reported at least on a semester basis in the project internal reports.

Table 7 – CROPS Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures

Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Implementation difficulties due to personnel changes at partner organisations	WP4, WP1, WP3, WP6, WP2, WP5	Flexibility in added resources or making use of other partner expertise; engaging external specialists.
Lack of internal resources to complete all tasks as planned	WP1	Target effort on areas with the highest potential of success. Planning for cross partnership support allows other partners to support the activity or event.
Opt-out of a consortium member	WP1	The likelihood will be kept low through continuous consultation, high-frequency communication, and clear conflict-resolution procedures. If one of the partners is forced to withdraw, the consortium will invite suitable members from industry or academia to replace the missing party, thus minimising the negative impact.
Failure to produce deliverables on time or to sufficient quality	WP1	The project plan (D1.1) will set out a rigorous framework for delivery, including internal peer review. Reports and key outputs will be developed in stages so that basic functionality is reached relatively early, and a lack of progress can be detected.
Financial divergences	WP1	Potential excess of the estimated budget might occur. The consortium and mainly the coordinator will review the budget issues throughout the project duration very carefully and monitor costs closely to anticipate potential excess on time and suggest responsive action.
Impossibility/unavailability of JRC for actively	WP2	The AB has been structured to include experts from each of the 5 EU missions. These can and will be leveraged to invite domain experts to the respective mission-specific workshops. The overall

Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
participating in the assessment workshop		positioning of the consortium also ensures high outreach among these disciplines and communities.
Difficulties in assuring the adequate participation of stakeholders	WP4, WP3, WP5	Partners have extensive networks of contacts that will be mobilized since the beginning of the project to assure awareness and adherence to the project activities, such as surveys, interviews, and mutual learning workshops.
Collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives is not mutually beneficial or not effective and efficient	WP4, WP1, WP3, WP6, WP2, WP5	CROPS will plan early the engagement and possible bridges with the selected EU projects and initiatives by identifying mutual interests and cooperation areas. Meetings will be set with the coordinators of the other actions for stimulating common understanding on objectives and collaboration areas.
Epidemics or other crises affecting international engagement and activities	WP4, WP1, WP3, WP6, WP2, WP5	Many meetings and most project support provided are planned to be online. If restrictions hinder in-person meetings and workshop activities, the consortium will review the project plan and put more effort into communication and online support.

CROPS Risk Management Plan embraces the following activities:

- Identifying the key risks in delivering this project and anticipating how the risk will be managed within the project.
- Creating a risk reporting channel. Each partner should have the opportunity to identify perceived and/or real risks.
- Assigning who should be responsible for foreseeing potential project problems.
- Preparing mitigation plans for agreed risks. The purpose of the mitigation plan is to describe how the particular risk would be handled – what would be done, when, by who and how to avoid the risk or minimize the consequences if it becomes a liability.
- Balancing the costs of undertaking risk mitigation activities against the cost of exposure to the risk.

7 Conclusion

D1.1 Project Management Plan serves as a comprehensive framework and guideline that outlines how the partners will ensure the efficient management of the CROPS project. The project partners are fully committed to fulfilling their respective responsibilities as mentioned throughout the document. However, they also acknowledge that as the project progresses, new guidelines and practices may need to be established to address evolving needs or challenges. In such cases, the Management Plan will be updated accordingly. Any updates or changes made to the document will be communicated to all partners and duly reported in the prefinancing and/or periodic report.